

**Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering
Institute of Chemical and Environmental Engineering
Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava**

PROCEEDINGS

34th International Conference of Slovak Society of Chemical Engineering

**Hotel Hutník
Tatranské Matliare, Slovakia
May 21 – 25, 2007**

Editors: J. Markoš and V. Štefuca

ISBN 978-80-227-2640-5

Optimization of turbogenerator performance by means of steam expansion adiabatic efficiency analysis

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Key words: optimization, steam expansion adiabatic efficiency, turbogenerator, energetic set, steam consumption diagram

Introduction

Increasing the efficiency of energy production by optimization of energetic sets is current interest of all energy producing companies. There are several ways how to perform analysis of such sets, with exergetic analysis being the most popular and most frequently used. For the purpose of investigation of steam expansion in a turbogenerator, the exergetic analysis transforms in steam expansion adiabatic efficiency study. However, this analysis is omitted very frequently and steam consumption diagram together with specific energy production per unit of mass of steam are used by engineers instead. In this paper we demonstrate, how important the steam expansion adiabatic efficiency analysis is in evaluation of energy transformation in a turbogenerator. Furthermore, we show that only by combining those tools one can examine the steam expansion correctly in order to optimise the energy output of the whole set. To test this approach, an energetic set in an industrial company in Slovakia has been subjected to steam expansion adiabatic efficiency study. This paper sums up its description, analysis and discussion of results in the light of verification of our approach to optimization.

Set description

The complete energetic set consists of three boilers B1, B2 and B3 and of three turbogenerators TG1, TG2 and TG3. Boilers B1 and B2 combust a low combustion heat fuel from technology, whereby the inorganic part of it is regenerated and can be recycled to technology. Boiler B3 combusts another low combustion heat fuel and serves as a peak boiler. Boiler B1 produces life steam with parameters 8 MPa and 460 °C, which is led into turbogenerator TG1. Boilers B2 and B3 produce qualitatively different life steam with parameters 4.2 MPa and 400 °C. This life steam is led into turbogenerators TG2 and TG3. Other characteristic features of the boilers are shown in **Tab.1**.

Boiler	Thermal efficiency (%)	Additional fuel	Feed water temperature (°C)
B1	81	Earth gas	116
B2	72	-	125 – 145
B3	87	Earth gas	125 – 145

Tab.1: Actual values of characteristic properties of boilers B1 – B3.

Turbogenerator TG1 supplies the technology with low pressure (0.6 MPa) steam. It plays very important role in the whole set, for usually more than 50% of total output is generated here. Thus, its optimal performance is crucial for the efficiency of the set. Its nominal steam consumption is 145 t/h, but because of high electricity production potential of the life steam which is led into it, it is often overloaded to get higher output. Therefore, it is operated at 145 t/h and above through

substantial part of year. At nominal steam mass flow it generates 133 kWh per 1t of expanding steam, which is more than specific energy production per unit of mass of steam expanding in TG2 and TG3 (see below).

Turbogenerators TG2 and TG3 cover the remaining technological demand for middle pressure (1.3 MPa) extraction steam as well as low pressure (0.6 MPa) steam. Their nominal steam consumption is 135 t/h each, with extraction steam mass flow varying from 20 to 60 t/h each to saturate its technological demands. Because of the seasonal dependence of steam demands in technology, these turbogenerators are operated at up to 130 t/h each in winter and at 90 – 100 t/h each in summer. At nominal steam mass flow (135 t/h, 30 t/h extraction steam) it generates 89 kWh per 1t of expanding steam.

Amounts of steam generated in B1 and B2 by combusting the low combustion heat fuel are given by the specific electricity production per mass unit of steam led into TG1, TG2 and TG3. These values can easily be calculated from steam consumption diagrams of turbogenerators at various loads. However, all steam consumption diagrams were calculated assuming different steam parameters from what they are like. **Tab.2** gives an overview of calculated and actual life steam parameters.

Turbogenerator	Pressure (MPa)		Temperature (°C)	
	designed	actual	designed	actual
TG1	8.4	7.5	480	455
TG2 and TG3	4.3	4.0	400	400

Tab.2: Designed and actual life steam parameters.

One can see that life steam parameters entering TG1 are much different from designed ones, whereas life steam entering TG2 and TG3 differs from designed value only in pressure. As a result, life steam enthalpy led into TG1 is lower by 40 MJ/t and its entropy nearly the same when compared to designed values. This influences the output of TG1, lowering it by appr. 10%. Calculated enthalpic change of life steam led into TG2 and TG3 is negligible, but there is significant entropy increase of $0.02 \text{ MJ t}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$. This entropic shift impacts the TG2 and TG3 performance by lowering it. It was therefore questionable, what effect those changes would have on the performance of the whole set and it had to be incorporated in our study.

Data evaluation

We have been kindly provided with one hour average online data for the year 2006, including feed water temperature, life, middle pressure and low pressure steam parameters, boiler steam outputs and steam mass flows through turbogenerators. Online data from industry monitoring system have been subjected to detailed analysis in order to reconstruct steam consumption diagram of TG1 using steam expansion adiabatic efficiency analysis as an effective tool. Steam adiabatic efficiency is given by following expression.

$$\eta_{ad} = \frac{h_{ls} - h_{out}}{h_{ls} - h_{out}^{ad}} \quad (1)$$

The meaning of symbols used is as follows: h_{ls} – enthalpy of life steam entering turbogenerator, h_{out} – enthalpy of steam leaving turbogenerator, h_{out}^{ad} – enthalpy of steam leaving turbogenerator after adiabatic expansion. In common, for a given turbogenerator, steam expansion adiabatic efficiency η_{ad} is a non-linear function of steam mass flow into a turbogenerator, ranging from near zero values at low steam mass flow and increasing with growing mass flow. Its value represents deviation from isentropic expansion, being the most effective way of converting life

steam enthalpy into electrical work towards simple steam pressure reduction associated with zero electrical work obtained. Values of over 0.8 are usually connected with sophisticated turbogenerator construction and steam mass flow near the designed value.

Calculated steam expansion adiabatic efficiency versus steam mass flow through TG1 and TG2 is plotted in **Fig.1**. For TG1 it exhibits an unusual shape, obviously dividing the operating conditions of TG1 in two regimes. The first one, associated with lower steam mass flow, is a regular case of steam expansion in a sophisticated turbogenerator, characterized by increasing steam expansion adiabatic efficiency with increasing mass flow through the turbogenerator. After passing through a maximum at appr. 125 t/h steam mass flow, however, adiabatic efficiency curve starts to decrease progressively. As a result, less electrical energy is produced per mass unit of expanding steam and the low pressure steam is leaving TG1 at higher temperature. By comparison with steam expansion in TG2, expansion adiabatic efficiency of TG1 is higher at all steam mass flow values, retaining a value over 0.78 even at 60% of the designed steam mass flow. TG2 generates electricity most effectively when operated at full load, which is an expectable conclusion.

Fig.1: Steam expansion adiabatic efficiency of TG1 – squares and TG2(3) – diamonds.

To verify our assumption that this irregular behaviour of steam expansion adiabatic efficiency would have serious impact on steam consumption diagram of TG1, we calculated actual steam consumption diagrams for TG1 and TG2 (TG3). In **Fig.2a,b** actual steam consumption diagrams are compared with designed ones. On the left hand figure, two profound effects of steam expansion adiabatic efficiency irregularity on steam consumption diagram can be qualitatively

Fig. 2a,b: Steam consumption diagrams for TG1 (a) and TG2 (b), output (kW) plotted versus steam mass flow (t/h). a: full symbols – upper branch of diagram, empty symbols – lower branch of diagram; diamonds – designed state, squares – actual state; b: diamonds – designed state at 30 t/h extraction steam mass flow, squares – actual state at 30 t/h extraction steam mass flow.

described. Firstly, at the same steam mass flow, where maximum of expansion adiabatic efficiency is achieved, the linear dependence of turbogenerator output on steam mass flow breaks and continues as another line with different slope at higher steam mass flows. Secondly, by changing parameters of life steam entering TG1, not only the intercepts, but also the slopes of linear dependences were changed. This resulted in shift of breaking point from 134 t/h to 125 t/h mass flow. Changing the inlet pressure of life steam into TG2(3) resulted only in significant change of intercept of steam consumption diagram, while the slope remained nearly the same. **Tab.3** gives an overview of steam consumption diagram parameters.

Turbogenerator	Designed state		Actual state	
	Slope, kWh/t	Intercept, kW	Slope, kWh/t	Intercept, kW
TG1 upper branch	91.2	8378	99.7	4236
TG1 lower branch	179.1	-3397	152.4	-2232
TG2(3)	128.9	-4271	123.2	-4562

Tab.3 Designed and actual parameters of steam consumption diagrams of TG1,2 and 3.

Discussion

Results from both **Fig.1** as well as from **Fig.2 a,b** point toward optimization procedure of turbogenerators performance: in order to achieve the highest overall electrical energy production per unit of expanding steam, TG1 has to be operated at 125 t/h steam mass flow and the remaining steam production has to be divided equally between TG2 and TG3.

Obviously, operating a turbogenerator cannot be optimized separately from boiler performance and total available fuel to be regenerated production is an important factor as well. Because the same fuel is combusted in B1 as well as in B2, an optimization procedure covering performance of B1, B2, B3, and TG1, TG2 and TG3 was necessary. Central task of optimization was to estimate such operating conditions which lead to maximal electricity production with respect to the possibility to cover the rest of steam consumption demand by B3. **Tab.3** sums up important facts about boilers B1 and B2, highlighting specific heat consumption per 1t of live steam generated. Due

Boiler	Feed water enthalpy, MJ/t	Live steam enthalpy, MJ/t	Specific heat consumption in boiler, MJ/t	Specific heat consumption in boiler incorporating its thermal efficiency, MJ/t
B1	485	3310	2835	3500
B2	525 - 610	3210	2600 - 2685	3610 - 3730

Tab.3: Operating conditions and parameters of boilers B1 and B2.

to lower thermal efficiency, in order to generate the same amount of live steam, boiler B2 has to combust by 3 – 7 % more fuel than B1. From this point of view, boiler B1 should be operated at its nominal steam output and the rest of fuel should be combusted in B2. But after considering the subsequent electrical energy generation in TG1, TG2 and TG3, different result is obtained. 1 t of live steam generates in TG1 appr. 100 kWh at loads over 125 t/h, whereas in TG2 or TG3 appr. 123 kWh are generated, which is more by 23 %. This fact outweighs the slightly higher specific heat consumption in B2. Thus, the final optimization procedure of the whole set is identical with that of the turbogenerators, yielding the optimal steam output of B1 at 125 t/h with the rest of available fuel to be combusted in B2. Small deficit in steam production resulting from this optimization procedure can in most cases be readily covered by increasing the steam output of B3.

In order to quantify the increase in efficiency of electricity production, we evaluated data from online measurements in terms of changed steam mass flow through turbogenerators and of increased electrical production. A typical outcome of our optimization procedure is depicted in **Fig.3a,b**.

As it is apparent from **Fig.3a**, optimized values of steam mass flow through TG1 are at the same value all day, while those through TG2, 3 increased but mostly retained their daily course. An exception can be seen in the afternoon, where actual and optimized values come closer together. These facts had impact on overall electrical energy production plotted versus time in **Fig.3b** – the more the steam mass flow differ after optimization from actual values, the bigger the electrical energy gain compared to actual overall turbogenerator output. Electrical energy gain ranges up to 700 kW, which is an up to 2% increase in overall turbogenerator output. Furthermore, this optimization procedure does not involve any additional investment costs.

Fig.3a,b: Steam mass flows through turbogenerators in t/h (a) and their overall output in kW (b).
a: diamonds – total steam mass flow through turbogenerators, squares – steam mass flow through TG2 and TG3, triangles – steam mass flow through TG1; full symbol – actual value, empty symbol – optimized value. **b:** full diamond – actual overall electrical energy production, empty diamond – optimized overall electrical energy production.

Conclusions

Turbogenerator performance has been studied in order to achieve its optimum in an industrial company in Slovakia. Steam expansion adiabatic efficiency analysis was successfully applied in optimization process. It revealed an unusual trend of steam expansion adiabatic efficiency as a function of steam mass flow through the turbogenerator TG1 which had a profound impact on its steam consumption diagram. The dramatic change of trend in this diagram pointed to optimal operating it at constant steam mass flow by changing the amounts of fuel combusted in boilers B1 and B2. By application of this optimization procedure on real energetic set we managed to increase the total turbogenerator output by up to 700 kW. Therefore we can conclude that a consistent approach to turbogenerator optimization, comprising steam expansion adiabatic efficiency studies and steam consumption diagram analysis proves advantageous over simple computations based on specific electrical energy production values.